

Workshop: Putting design at the heart: Weaving empathy into service design methods

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Topic Designers strive to create things that make an impact on people by viewing their work through a human-centered lens. Whether it's speaking to the people who will be using a service or product, or shadowing those who will be at the heart of a new process, an emotional understanding of human needs is both fundamental and transformational in design work. Human-centered design is empathetic by definition, as it places people at the center of the creative process. However once the process starts, designers don't often get to address how empathy is reflected in their methods and design artifacts.

Designers can go beyond approaching their work with design empathy alone – they have to work within the constituency that they are designing for. This workshop will touch on approaching design work with “deep empathy” and how weaving this type of approach into design methods and artifacts is a powerful way to capture emotion and ensure that design empathy endures.

Purpose As designers, we strive to embody empathetic design. But too often, our design methods fail to make the most of the time we spend with the people for whom we're designing or working. The Design and Emotion conference is an ideal setting to invite designers to contemplate the level of design empathy that informs their work from start to finish.

The purpose of this session is to inspire designers to weave “deep empathy” and emotion into their design methods. We'll explain how this led to success, using our work within the social services space as an example. The workshop will equip participants with an understanding of how a careful choice of design methods will help them design with empathy and make a lasting impact.

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